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методов обучения и воспитания, а также в практических аспектах взаимодействия с детьми. Более глубокое изучение этой темы потребует анализа фольклорных сюжетов с точки зрения их воздействия на различные аспекты развития детей через призму современных теорий психологии и развития.

Таким образом, культура оказывает значительное влияние на психологическое развитие детей. Понимание этого влияния позволяет родителям, педагогам и психологам учитывать культурные особенности при воспитании и обучении детей, что способствует их гармоничному развитию.

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SPECIFIC FEATURES OF INTEGRATIVE AND MOTIVATIONAL OF TEACHING PHYSICAL EDUCATION STUDENTS

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Abstract. *In this article discussed about the integrative and motivational features of foreign language teaching for the students of physical education and sports of higher education. The key to great success for athletes is the result of integrated education, which brings out internal and external unity of motivations.*

Key words: *motivation, external/internal motivation, ESP, communicative, speech communication, integration, integrative method, interdisciplinary intersection, competence, joint teaching, lingua, motivation, success.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada oliy ta'lim muassasalarining 2-bosqich jismoniy tarbiya va sport fakulteti talabalariga chet tilini o'rgatishning integrativ va motivatsion xususiyatlari va bu motivatsiyaning ahamiyati ko'rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, sportchilarning katta muvaffaqiyatlari, ular ko'rsatayotgan ko'rsatkichlari va yutuqlariga erishishining kaliti motivlarning ichki va tashqi birligini ochib beradigan har tomonlama tayyorgarlik ekanligi xususida fikrlar bildirilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *motivatsiya, ekstrasensory idrok, aloqa, og'zaki muloqot, integratsiya, integrativ usul, fanlararo kesishish, kompetentsiya, hamkorlikda o'rganish, til, motivatsiya, muvaffaqiyat.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются интегративные и мотивационные особенности обучения иностранному языку студентов вузов физической культуры и спорта.*

Залогом больших успехов спортсменов является результат интегрированного обучения, при котором происходит внутреннее и внешнее единство мотивов.

Ключевые слова: *мотивация, внешняя/внутренняя мотивация, ESP, коммуникативная, речевая коммуникация, интеграция, интегративный метод, междисциплинарное пересечение, компетенция, совместное обучение, лингва, мотивация, успех.*

Concepts such as motivation, raising morally and gaining interest are one of the most important factors in learning and teaching a new language, and serve as the main factor in increasing the strength of the learner's desire and will to acquire knowledge and master new materials. Motivation also differs depending on the choice of the source is being mastered, and through the mental activity of a person, it ensures its practice by enjoying the activity of the mind. This is Motivation, which essentially gives the human mind a deep need to receive and learn new information with a strong desire of its body, and the impetus for the practical implementation of internal and external wishes and desires. It manifests itself in filling weak points in a certain field and skill of the human factor, in seeking at a high level, in conquering unbelievable milestones. Filip M. Olsson conducts experimental work connecting the concept of Sports Motivation Scale (SMS) with (IM) intrinsic motivation and (EM) extrinsic motivation and the following qualities are describes and evaluates factors such as difficulty-skill balance, integration of action and awareness, clear goals, feedback, task focus, sense of control, and explains the stimulation of intrinsic motivation to achieve success [2]. Motivation plays scientifically a key role in easy and effective learning of foreign languages and wide use of opportunities. It is evidence of the high level of opportunity currently mentioned that it is as a scientific and practical need, also to raise it to the level of state policy. The president of Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev, a video selector meeting, it was held on Nov 6, 2021 regarding measures to improve the system of teaching foreign languages, and at that meeting, the president presents a new system for teaching foreign languages that will be a solid foundation for the future. It is time to start," his comments are admirable and form a motivational incentive and a sense of obligation in the minds of the youth of our country to learn foreign languages [1]. Encouraging language development in physical education may seems difficulty and identifying and meeting the language needs of ELLs with an integrative approach can be challenging. However, properly developed integrative methods and selected methods are the main factor in solving such problems. The word "integration" derived from the Latin word "integer", which gives the concept of scientific and technical cooperation of several other disciplines under the concept

of one subject and helps to develop positive social relations in students are demonstrated the quality educational experience it provides [3].

When it comes to the successful impact of language learning in a meaningful and mutually integrated manner with physical education, there is a need to implement a bilingual program in physical education (PE) itself, and precisely because of this need The use of English as a programming language opens the door to many and wide opportunities for young students. In order for CLIL and PE is combined in the same audience, to act together, attention should be paid to the creation of constructive discussions and relationships during the lesson, that is, to learn new language for special purposes (ESP) skills and competencies as a team. It is important to create a favorable environment for development. In fact, during the course of the physical culture lesson, a situation both of them created for the use of communication process units related to natural, real language (CLIL). (EOP) English for professional purposes and (EAP/ESP) English for academic, that is, English for special purposes in a condition where lexical-grammatical and oral needs is combined, to create and teach educational programs in an interdisciplinary relationship

clarifies. PhD (DC's), prof. D.M.Isroilova of The state of interdisciplinary English education of students in the non-philological higher educational institutions was thoroughly theoretically and competitively analyzed, scientific pedagogical experience is being carry out through a new teaching scheme, and as a result, a new concept of "field of needs" was introduced in the methodology. Proposals are emphasized the need to take into account interdisciplinary in the training of highly qualified specialists, the importance of scientific-theoretical integration of regional and socio-economic fields for specialists [4]. The academic-theoretical study of English in the professional field and the ability to use it in practice will lead to the development, development and importance of the professional language among students who are interested in multilingualism. Being a competent user of academic language, according to Gottlieb and Ernst Slavik, means knowing what to say, when to say it, and how to use it in different oral and written disciplinary contexts [5].

It supports the development of the ability to solve problems that may be it encountered in professional development. In language learning in the audience, only theory or verbal instructions are not enough, words must be connected and modeled with their physical counterparts, saying-forgetting, showing-remembering, involvement, i.e. practice- provides understanding. Students do not want to use oral skills in a regular English class, it concluded that they used their English speaking skills through physical responses during the physical practice lessons and were able to force them to use these English skills regularly [6].

According to several experts who have theorized empirical research on CLIL PE, the activities should not only include physical activity, but also an understanding of health and physicality. The most importantly, they should promote a high level of dialogical communication, cooperation. Their believe that it should include language and content representation through speech and movement, and that such interaction is important for improving language and physical education skills. Nathan J. Devos states that CLIL PE needs developed along with the development of new practical curricula due to its active collaborative, motivational and multi-sensory characteristics [7].

During the exchange program, in order to prevent the emergence of internal intrinsic emotional and external extrinsic obstacles related to language and communication in the student, to develop motivations for language learning in the student, both sides in mastering new language materials. There is a great need for the creation of a common and jointly developed database of solutions that support.

The Sports Student Exchange Program (SSEP) is a sports student exchange program, in which students of sports-related specialties exchange places within the scope of two or more higher education institutions within a certain time. The acquisition of English as the only means of communication during this program, which it is carried internationally, also facilitates the process of communication, cooperation in the production of educational programs, manuals, joint publications, creation of literature, and the establishment of mutual events and conference relations also it is recognized as the only alternative language in conducting organic research and optimization, generalization and.

The need is to awaken motivation in students, to achieve intellectual achievements, to gain top positions on the podiums of the world sports arena, to continue their effective work in educational institutions, or to participate in international competitions as a trainer, coach, referee of the international category. It is also a program for them to do solid practice on the Content Learned Integrating Language (CLIL) system. Collaborative Teaching (CT) is effective in the faster and easier passage of psychological processes that occur in subconscious activities, such as comprehensibility, memorability, reinforcement, when a physical culture trainer and an English

language teacher conduct joint teaching activities. The participation of students in the learning process and their satisfaction with the training are important in increasing the usefulness of the programs created, as a result, the joint work of the teachers of both subjects. The framework of cultural interaction created between them should be moderated, the negative impact of the new culture should be prevented, barriers of a cultural and spiritual nature, which can be found on the Internet, should be discussed in the process of reflection. The importance of the national integrative approach and the given motivation is also great in the correct implementation of the process of emotional, internal and external attitude to learning. In the process of organized (CLIL) integrative education, the object is clear, the goals chose correctly for the problem, the new topic, and the effective use of methods and new technologies introduced in education in their place, achieves positive and expected results are important. Jan Amon Comenius, recognized as a great didactic figure in pedagogy, emphasizes that everything related to each other should have taught in the same relationship without any changes. This factor, which affects the academic potential of every student sitting in the audience, controls internal and external desire, unites, seeks opportunities, and prevents laziness are also recognized as one of the most relevant sports, English language and motivation in the life of an athlete shows that it is done. So, behind the victory of the athlete lies the internal and external motivation, continuous physical movements, flawless thoughts and judgments, and the effective work of teachers and coaches behind how well the language norms mastered.

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INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA MUBOLAG'ALASHGAN FRAZEOLOGIK BIRLIKLARNING TILLARARO KORRESPONDENSIYASI

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Annotatsiya. *Maqola tilshunoslikda frazeologik birlikning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini tahlil qilishga bag'ishlangan bo'lib unda ingliz va o'zbek tillarida frazeologik birlikning o'рни hamda axborot yetkazishdagi roli va ularning stilistik xususiyatlari yoritilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *frazeologik birlik, tilshunoslik, ekvivalentlik, ekspressiv, kognitiv, emosema.*

